

Received: 26 Feb 2021/ Accepted: 03 Mar 2021/ Published: 30 April 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730879>

Evaluation of phenolic content along with antioxidant potential of Guggul

Shweta Hingwasiya^{1*}, Shailbala Baghel²

¹Govt. P.G. College Narsinghar, Barkatullah University-462026 (M.P.), India

²Sarojini Naidu Govt. P.G. Girls College Bhopal, Barkatullah University-462026 (M.P.), India

Corresponding author: Shweta Hingwasiya (shw_sha@yahoo.co.in)

This work was presented at the *International Conference on Biomaterials and Biosensor Technologies* held during 12-13, March 2021 at *Bannari Amman Institute of Technology*

Introduction: Plants have been used since ancient times as an important source of biologically active substances (1). The aim of the present study was to investigate the phytochemical constituents (Phenolics) and the antioxidant activity of the *Commiphora mukul* (Guggul). Phenol content was analyzed by spectrophotometer at 765 nm respectively. The free radical scavenging activity was evaluated by DPPH method. This study provides a definitive report about the free radical scavenging activity of *Commiphora mukul*.

Methods: Preparation of alcoholic extract of in *Commiphora mukul* by Reflux condenser: Take 50gm of sample in a flask of vortex condenser and add 150 ml of methanol. Adjust the temperature of heating methanol at 40°C and the reaction was kept for 2 days. Decent the supernatant in a beaker and discard the waste of plant sample. Evaporate the methanol by keeping beaker in water bath at 40 to 60 °C. After complete evaporation, dissolve the powder in 100 ml distilled water. Centrifuge the solution for 15 minutes. The supernatant was collected, and the concentration of extract was determined.

The total phenol was estimated in alcoholic extracts of *Commiphora mukul* using Folin-Ciocalteu method (2). DPPH free radical scavenging activity was estimated by measuring the decrease in the absorbance of methanolic solution of DPPH (2,2-diphenyl 1-picryl hydrazyl).

Results & Discussions: The percentage of free radical scavenging activities were performed. It was found that ascorbic acid exhibited higher DPPH free radical Scavenging activity than the compound at all concentrations. But, at concentration 700 µg/ml scavenging activities of *Commiphora mukul* were found to be very close to the ascorbic acid. This shows that antioxidant activity evaluated by DPPH free radical Scavenging, indicates that the resin can be used as source of natural antioxidant reagent. FolinCiocalteu method is recognized as nonspecific for phenolic compounds.

Conclusions: From the present study it may be concluded that alcoholic extract of *Commiphora mukul* showed protective as well as therapeutic efficiency to cope up the oxidative stress.

Key words: Antioxidants, *Commiphora mukul*, Free radical Scavenging Activity

References

1. Johnson F, Giulivi Superoxide dismutases and their impact upon human health” Mol Aspects Med Vol26.2005 p 340 -52.
2. Singleton, V.L. Orthofer, R lamuclaReventos, RM. Analysis of total phenol and other oxidation substances and antioxidant by means of follin – ciolaten reagent. In methods in enzymology, packer ,packer,L,Ed,Vol 249 Academic press 1994 p 152-59.

